

TECHNOLOGIES OF USING INNOVATIVE METHODS IN HISTORY LESSONS

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Abstract: In this article, in the organization of history lessons, the establishment of interdisciplinary communication and the division of lessons into certain groups based on topics, the scientific worldview of students with the help of concepts in the lessons that are close to each other in terms of content or mixed subjects, and characteristics such as the formation of specific skills and qualifications are revealed.

Key words: history, digital history, didactic conditions, map, interdisciplinarity, integration, innovative methods.

Educational practice shows that establishing interdisciplinarity in school education is a vivid expression of the integration processes taking place in the life of science and society today. This connection plays an important role in students' conscious acquisition of knowledge, development of their holistic vision of the world, and improvement of their practical and scientific-methodical preparation. Such training gives general secondary education graduates the opportunity to freely apply the knowledge, skills and abilities they have acquired in class and extracurricular activities, in production and in general in any activity. summarizing the experiences of teachers in:

1. In a lesson organized on the basis of demonstrability, based on the representation of interdisciplinary elements in different tables and models, which are used to perform separate tasks related to the topic being studied. to study such topics as "Culture of Asian countries", "Medieval cities in Europe", "Medieval cities of Asian countries".
2. Similarity of topics: increasing the effectiveness of the lesson based on the use of interdisciplinary communication as an integral part of the educational process.
3. Generalization - in order to perfectly teach the general laws and principles of academic subjects, it is possible to repeat the acquired knowledge of students in specially organized repetition-generalization classes in various academic subjects.

If the following didactic conditions are followed in the course of the lesson, the effectiveness of the embodied approach to teaching will be achieved: it is necessary to include interdisciplinary lesson hours in the curriculum by

combining the topics of the studied subjects. Effective use of various means of accelerating students' cognitive activities in ensuring interdisciplinary communication. For example, it is possible to achieve such a goal with the help of the organization of problem solving, demonstration, independent works, individual tasks in mixed educational courses. The use of other lesson materials in order to deepen the students' assimilation of the lesson materials studied on the basis of interdisciplinary communication, and the fact that these materials are mutually related in terms of content. In this, there may be repetition, generalization, learning of new material, strengthening of skills and competences, and control lessons. Interdisciplinarity further enriches these conflicts of the educational process, on the basis of which new contradictions arise. These are contradictions between mastering the knowledge learned from the educational subject and solving problems on the basis of interdisciplinary connections and knowing how to apply them in mastering knowledge from other different disciplines.

The following didactic requirements are imposed on the lessons conducted on the basis of interdisciplinary communication:

1. In order to master a new subject in a lesson studied on the basis of interdisciplinarity, the knowledge acquired from other disciplines should be involved and to acquire the skills to apply them.
2. In the course of the lesson, it should be aimed at explaining the essence and cause-and-effect relationships of the studied phenomena on the basis of interdisciplinary communication.
3. The lesson conducted on the basis of the application of interdisciplinary communication should create positive impressions in the students, create interest in them to learn the differences and connections between the knowledge they have received from different subjects.

In the organization of integrated lessons, a personalized approach implies giving importance to each child, not just to a class or group. In this, his personal qualities and abilities are shown separately, and his interests are taken into account. For this purpose, you can use games such as "Explanation of terms", "Find the pair", "Aql Khaxpalagi". During the game, attention is focused on one child. (For example, each child says a term for the first letter of his name. In the "Find the pair" game, 5 handouts with questions and their answers are distributed to students. 10 students should pair up with the correct answers to the questions based on the handouts. It is intended to encourage originality, perseverance, dexterity in acquiring knowledge and solving artistic life issues. In

this regard, it is necessary to form the ability of children to think independently, work on themselves and compare different eras. Therefore, the integration of education is the demand of the present time.

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